

Mudharaba on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the map of the development of research regarding Mudharabah contracts at Islamic Financial Institutions with a VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. The research was conducted over a period of 21 years from 2001 to 2021 by searching through the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) with the keyword Mudharabah/Mudharabah. And obtained 857 research articles. The search results were analyzed then descriptively, inputted, analyzed using VOSViewer and Library Research to determine the visualization of topic developments and research around the Mudharabah contract. The results showed that the number of publications regarding Mudharabah contracts has increased significantly every year. Then, based on the results of research visualization using VOSviewer, the Mudharabah contract is divided into 8 clusters. Based on the results of the Library Research, there are 8 main themes and 435 research topics regarding Mudharabah contracts at Islamic Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Mudaraba; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Institutions

Introduction

The practice of mudharabah contracts has an important role in increasing sharia-based economic development in Indonesia. Several reasons for the importance of this contract include: (1) it can replace the interest/usury system with a system based on sharia principles to develop an Islamic economy (Trimulato, 2016); (2) contract products in Sharia Financial Institutions are not solely aimed at making a profit, but are also social/mutually helpful (Syarifuddin, 2012); and (3) in this agreement, Sharia Financial Institutions can become a tool to improve the economic welfare of society (Sunardi, 2021).

This agreement is always found in every product at a Sharia Financial Institution, such as sharia banking, financing institutions, insurance institutions, venture capital companies and pension fund companies. Thus, mudharabah contract products are one of the favorites for the public in choosing services, both in fund storage and financing products. In Sharia Financial Institutions, mudharabah contracts are one of the funds collection and financing products. (Wiroso: 2011).

Scientific publications regarding mudharabah contracts also continue to increase from year to year based on searches via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital). Even in 2021, there were 156 studies regarding Mudharabah contracts. This shows that the development of Mudharabah contracts is very rapid as one of the sharia product choices for the community.

The aim of this research is to determine a map of the development of research regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions over a period of 21 years using the VOSviewer bibliometric method and Library Research.

Literature Review

A Mudharabah contract is a cooperative agreement in managing assets, in which the capital owner (shahibul mal) provides all the capital, and the capital manager (mudharib). Then, the profits from managing the funds are divided between the two parties according to the agreement stated in the contract (KHES, Chapter VIII, Article 231 and DSN-MUI Fatwa, No. 07, 2000).

Bibliometric studies are the application of mathematical and statistical methods to the publication of books, articles and other information media. The aim is to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field.

VOSviewer is a software tool for creating, exploring and visualizing metadata network maps. It can be concluded that this tool has two main functions: (1) Creating bibliometric maps based on metadata networks. The map can create a network of scientific publications, journals, researchers, institutions, countries, keywords that are available or not yet available; and (2) Visualizing and exploring bibliometric maps. VOSviewer provides three forms of visualization, namely network, overlay and density visualization.

Library Research is the process of analyzing and identifying research articles on a particular theme. With this process, the steps for reviewing articles from journals, final assignments and seminar proceedings can be systematic and structured.

Methodology

This research uses quantitative descriptive methods based on bibliometric investigations and Library Researchs. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions based on searches of the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital). The published articles come from accredited national journals. The limitations of the published articles used in this research are only those published in Open Access or can be accessed in terms of author, publisher, abstract, key words, year of publication and pdf.

Data collection for published articles was carried out from January 2001 to December 2021. The search technique was using the keywords " mudarabah " and " mudarabah " based on the title words category. Then the article data that meets these criteria is downloaded using the RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then imported into Mendeley software to store reference data and retrieve metadata in the article document. Next, the RIS data is processed and analyzed using the VOSViewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software. This is to find out bibliometric maps and trends in scientific publications regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions in Indonesia and globally over a period of 21 years.

Furthermore, by using a Library Research, this research attempts to describe the distribution of research topics, the amount of research in them and identify empty research spaces that need to be filled/completed regarding Mudharabah contracts at Sharia Financial Institutions.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

The results of searching scientific publications regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions during the period 2001 to 2021, show an increase in publications every year, especially in the last 5 years. And publication data was obtained in the form of articles totaling 857 titles originating from accredited national journals. In fact, in 2021, there will be 156 articles published. So, the average scientific publication regarding Mudharabah agreements is more than 40 articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Mudharabah contracts by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2001	1	2010	11	2016	69
2005	1	2011	13	2017	82
2006	1	2012	20	2018	108
2007	2	2013	45	2019	108
2008	5	2014	45	2020	135
2009	2	2015	53	2021	156
Total 857					

Source: Processed Data, Microsoft Excel 2013.

In table 2, there are 7 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions. The FEB Brawijaya University Student Scientific Journal is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results regarding Mudharabah contracts, which reaches 27 articles.

Table 2. Ranking of 10 institutions and journals that publish scientific publications regarding Mudharabah agreements

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
FEB Student Scientific Journal, Brawijaya University, Malang	27
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, Airlangga University	22
Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, STIE AAS Surakarta	9
Journal of Accounting Science and Research (JIRA), Indonesian College of Economics	9
Scientific Journal of Accounting Economics Students, Syiah Kuala University	7
el-Qist: Journal of Islamic Economic and Business (JIEB), Sunan Ampel State Islamic University	7
Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Muhammadiyah University Surabaya	7

Source: Processed Data, Microsoft Excel 2013.

Table 3 shows that the most productive researcher is Nana Diana from Singaperbangsa University, Kerawang, who wrote 6 articles.

Table 3. Productivity of researchers regarding Mudharabah contracts indexed in Google Scholar

Researcher	Number of Publications
Nana Diana (University of Singapore, Karawang)	6
Trimulato (Alauddin Makassar State Islamic University)	4
Muhammad Sjaiful (Halu Oleo University), Muhammad (Jogjakarta Islamic Economics College)	3
Emy Widyastuti (IAIN Salatiga), Bambang Waluyo (Jakarta State Polytechnic), Indah Wahyuningsih (University of Jember), Ibnu Rusydi (University of Wiralodra, Indramayu), Arini Mafarikhal Jannah (University of Surabaya), Istiqomah (General Soedirman University), Isnaini (University Medan Area), Vendra Irawan (Muhammadiyah University Yogyakarta), Mhd. Yadi Harahap (North Sumatra State Islamic University), Refky Fielnanda (Sulthan Thaha Saifuddin State Islamic University, Jambi)	2

Source: Processed Data, Microsoft Excel 2013.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

Research articles from searches on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, input and analyzed with VOSViewer. The results of the co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions are divided into 8 clusters, as follows.

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions. Data processed, VOSViewer 1.6.17 software.

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 101 topics, namely ability, agreement, mudharabah contract, assurance, bank, sharia bank, BMT, BSM, business

activity, capital, capital manager, capital owner, collateral, company, compliance, contract, conventional banking, credit, customer, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, data collection method, debt, debtor, distribution, DSN-MUI, economic growth, economy, education, entrepreneur, fatwa, financial institution, financial product, fiqh, goal, government, guarantee, high risk, important role, instrument, interest, investment, investor, Islam, Islamic banking, Islamic banking product, Islamic economics, Islamic financial institution, Islamic law, Islamic principle, Islamic sharia, knowledge, labor, law, legal risk, literature study, LKS, marketing strategy, medium enterprise, micro enterprise, mmob transaction, money, SMS, muamalah, mudharabah, mudharib, mudharabah, mudharabah contract, mudharabah financing, mudharabah muqayyadah, mudharabah product, mudharabah savings product, mudharabah system, mudharabah transaction, mudharib, MUI, murabahah, Muslims, musyarakah contract, national sharia council, obligation, opportunity, PBI, mudharabah financing, product, provision, real sector, regulation, risk management, saving, savings product, service, sharia, sharia bank, sharia banking, sharia principle, smes, society, sukuk, transaction, trust, usury, wadiah.

- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 42 topics, namely assets, Bank Indonesia, Bank Mandiri Syariah, bank size, banking, BI Rate, BOPO, BPR, BPRS, BUS, Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), conventional bank, deposits, mudharabah deposits, deposits ratio, descriptive analysis, TPF, equivalent rate, exchange rate, FDR, financial performance, financial services author, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Indonesia, inflation rate, interest rate, Islamic commercial bank, liquidity, mudharabah deposits, mudharabah savings, multiple regression analysis, Non Performing Financing (NPF), OJK, operational costs, profit sharing, profit sharing rate, profit sharing ratio, return mudharabah deposit, ROA, sharia commercial bank, sharia, third party funds.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 20 topics, namely Bank BRI Syariah, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Syariah Mandiri, BNI Syariah Bank, financial reports, financing, ijarah financing, murabahah financing, musyarakah financing, net income, net profit, net return, influence of mudharabah financing, influence of murabahah financing, problematic financing, profitability, quarterly financial statement, risk, sharia commercial banking, VAR.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 21 topics, namely accounting, accounting treatment, BNI Syariah, BMT Sidogiri, customer, demand, financial accounting statement, financing mudharabah, financial statement, fund, fund manager, KJKS BMT, majority, mudharabah accounting, policy, PSAK, SFAS, shahibul mal, sharia cooperative, sharing, sharia banking.
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 15 topics, namely agency problems, agents, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, clients, correlation, depositors, equity, moral hazard, mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing, ratio, return, ROE, ROMD, significant value.
- Cluster 6. The black color consists of 9 topics, namely data analysis, Islamic banking, loss sharing, mudharabah, mudharabah financing, murabahah margin income, operating income, profit, revenue sharing.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 4 topics, namely finance, KJKS, mudharabah agreement, UJKS.

- Cluster 8. The brown color consists of 1 topic, namely loan.

Mapping Research Topics and Subjects using Library Research Regarding Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

From search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), the distribution of research topics regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions includes eight main themes, namely: (1) Implementation of Mudharabah contracts; (2) The effect of the Mudharabah agreement; (3) Perspective of Islamic law, legislation and problems with Mudharabah contracts; (4) Indicators of customer loyalty, interest and satisfaction with Mudharabah contract products; (5) Efforts to develop Mudharabah contracts; (6) Factors that influence the Mudharabah contract; (7) Other problems related to the Mudharabah Agreement; and (8) Mudharabah Agreement on Sharia Bonds/Sukuk.

The explanation is as follows.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Application of Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

In this sub-chapter, the research subject regarding the application of Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions is divided into three parts, namely:

First, there are 14 research topics related to the application of Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions in general, with a total of 28 studies, namely: (-) Application of Mudharabah contracts, 10 studies; (-) Application of Mudharabah contracts in the profit sharing system, 4 studies; (-) Application of Mudharabah contracts to the wider community and the real sector, 2 research; (-) Application of Mudharabah contracts to other products, including: education fund products, idle land management, fairness in business, benchmarks for economic elements of civilization, forestry sector, non-cash transactions in notarial practice, livestock investment, multi Mudharabah Musytarakah contracts, sectors trade and insurance education. There is 1 research on each of these topics.

Second, there are 12 research topics related to the application of Mudharabah contract financing in Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 46 studies, namely: (-) Application of Mudharabah financing in Sharia Financial Institutions, 23 studies; (-) Application of Mudharabah financing according to the sharia/Islamic economic system, 5 studies; (-) Application of Mudharabah financing for business capital, 4 research; (-) Application of Mudharabah financing in the agricultural/real sector, 4 research; (-) Application of Mudharabah financing for the development of MSMEs, 3 research; (-) Application of other Mudharabah financing, including: working capital, marriage capital, fisheries sector, livestock sector, goat maparo, shrimp paste management business and halal national fund. There is 1 study each on these topics.

Third, there are 3 research topics related to the application of Mudharabah savings/deposits in Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 30 studies, namely: (1) Application of Mudharabah savings in savings products at Sharia Financial Institutions, 21 studies; (2) Application of Mudharabah savings in savings/deposit profit sharing, 8 studies; (3) Application of Mudharabah savings in Interbank/SIMA Mudharabah Investment Certificates, 1 research.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding The Influence of Mudharabah Agreements on Sharia Financial Institutions

In this sub-chapter, the research subject regarding the influence of Mudharabah agreements on Sharia Financial Institutions is divided into 3 parts, namely:

First, there are 7 research topics related to the influence of Mudharabah contracts on Sharia Financial Institutions in general, with a total of 9 studies, namely: (-) The influence of Mudharabah contracts on the profitability of Sharia Financial Institutions, 3 studies; (-) Other influences of the Mudharabah agreement include: realizing economic justice, alleviating poverty, developing MSMEs, Return On Assets / ROA levels, increasing company performance and profits. There is 1 research on each of these topics.

Second, there are 21 research topics related to the influence of Mudharabah financing on Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 142 studies, namely: (-) The influence of Mudharabah financing on the profitability of Sharia Financial Institutions, 55 studies; (-) The influence of Mudharabah financing on the development of MSMEs, 21 research; (-) The effect of Mudharabah financing on Return On Assets /ROA, 16 studies; (-) Effect of Mudharabah financing on net profit, 15 studies; (-) The effect of Mudharabah financing on Return On Equity /ROE, 6 studies; (-) The effect of Mudharabah financing on customer income, improving the customer/member economy and company income, 4 research on each of these topics; (-) The effect of Mudharabah financing on Non-Performing Financing /NPF, 3 studies; (-) The influence of Mudharabah financing in building Islamic Economics and company profitability, 2 research on each of these topics; (-) The influence of other Mudharabah financing, including: liquidity, Sharia Maqashid Index, profit sharing, cash receipts, volume of Mudharabah financing, economic growth, company value, regional income, total assets and Return On Investment. There is 1 research on each of these topics.

Third, there are 8 research topics related to the influence of Mudharabah savings/deposits in Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 8 studies, namely: (1) the influence of Mudharabah savings on fund distribution; (2) the effect of Mudharabah savings on Remaining Business Results/SHU; (3) the effect of Mudharabah savings on Return On Assets /ROA; (4) the influence of Mudharabah savings on MSME financing; (5) the influence of Mudharabah savings on bank financial performance; (6) the influence of Mudharabah savings on Mudharabah financing; (7) the effect of Mudharabah savings on profitability; and (8) the influence of Mudharabah savings on the Sharia Maqashid Index. There is 1 research on each topic.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Perspective of Islamic Law, Legislation and Problems of Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

In this sub-chapter, the research subject regarding the perspective of Islamic law, legislation and problems with Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions is divided into 3 parts, namely:

First, there are 10 research topics related to the perspective of Islamic law, legislation and problems with Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions in general, with a total of 47 studies, namely: (-) Application of Mudharabah transaction accounting in PSAK No. 105 on Sharia Financial Institutions, 16 studies; (-) Agency problems in Sharia Financial Institutions, 8 research; (-) Application of Mudharabah contracts according to Fiqh/Islamic Law/Sharia Economic Law, 8 studies; (-) Implementation of the Mudharabah contract according to the DSN-MUI Fatwa, 6 studies; (-) Implementation of the Mudharabah agreement according to Law no. 21 of 2008, 3 studies; (-)

Implementation of the Mudharabah contract according to several figures, 2 studies; (-) Implementation of Mudharabah transaction accounting in PSAK No. 106, 1 study; (-) Other problems in Mudharabah contracts, including: standard contract problems in Mudharabah contracts, risk mitigation according to legal aspects and BPKH's responsibility for Hajj funds invested in Mudharabah contracts. There is 1 study on these topics.

Second, there are 14 research topics related to the perspective of Islamic law, legislation and problems in Mudharabah financing at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 33 studies, namely: () Application of Mudharabah financing in PSAK No. 105 on Sharia Financial Institutions, 13 studies; (-) Guarantee problems in Mudharabah financing according to Law no. 21 of 2008 and DSN-MUI Fatwa, 3 studies; (-) Mudharabah financing according to jurisprudence and legislation, 3 research; (-) Concept of guarantee according to law and DSN-MUI fatwa in Mudharabah financing, 2 research; (-) Legal study of Mudharabah financing agreements, 2 research; (-) Other problems in Mudharabah financing, including: legal review of contract discrepancies in the disbursement of Mudharabah financing, conflicts in Mudharabah financing, problems in implementing accounting for Mudharabah financing, legal protection for sharia banks for customers in Sharia financing, agency problems in financing Mudharabah, dispute resolution between sharia banks and customers, Mudharabah financing according to Abdullah Saeed, legal protection for sharia banks for the death of the mudharib in Mudharabah financing and the juridical consequences of changing the object of mortgage rights in the Mudharabah financing contract. There is 1 research on each of these topics.

Third, there are 8 research topics related to the perspective of Islamic law, legislation and problems in Mudharabah deposit/savings products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 9 studies, namely: (-) The role of officials in implementing Mudharabah contracts, 2 studies; (-) Other problems in Mudharabah savings/savings, including: penalty fees on Mudharabah deposits according to Islamic law, implementation of Sharia compliance with profit sharing principles on Mudharabah savings, legal problems with Mudharabah savings, charging administration fees on Mudharabah deposit savings, determining the ratio profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits from the perspective of Islamic law, Mudharabah contracts in the Koran and Hadith and legal protection for deposit customers (BMI). There is 1 research on each of these topics.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Indicators of Customer Loyalty, Interest and Satisfaction with Mudharabah Agreement Products at Sharia Financial Institutions

In this sub-chapter, the research subject regarding indicators of customer loyalty, interest and satisfaction with Mudharabah contract products at Sharia Financial Institutions is divided into 7 parts, namely :

First, there are 5 indicators of customer loyalty towards Mudharabah financing products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 5 studies, namely: (1) Physical; (2) Reliability; (3) Fast response; (4) Insurance/guarantee; and (5) Empathy.

Second, there are 8 indicators of customer loyalty towards Mudharabah savings/savings products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 10 studies, namely: (-) Indicators of brand reputation and level of profit sharing, 2 studies on each indicator; (-) Other indicators include: fairness of profit sharing, brand equity, customer satisfaction, service quality, bank location and trust. There is 1 study on each indicator.

Third, there are 3 indicators of customer satisfaction with Mudharabah savings/deposit products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 5 studies, namely: (-) Service quality indicators, 3 research objects on this indicator; (-) Indicators of the value of bank products and facilities, 1 research object for each of these indicators.

Fourth, there are 2 indicators of customer satisfaction with Mudharabah contract products at Sharia Financial Institutions with a total of 2 studies, namely: (1) service quality; and (2) suitability in implementing the Mudharabah agreement.

Fifth, there are 9 indicators of customer interest in Mudharabah financing products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 13 studies, namely: (-) Service quality indicators, 3 research objects; (-) Sharia promotion and compliance indicators, 2 studies; (-) Other indicators include: religiosity factors, products, profit sharing system, profit perception, interest rates and guarantees. There is 1 study on each indicator.

Sixth, there are 21 indicators of customer interest in Mudharabah savings/savings products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 39 studies, namely: (-) Profit sharing level indicators, 9 studies; (-) Service quality indicators, 4 studies; (-) Bank location indicators, 2 studies; (-) Other indicators, including: brand image, deposit profit sharing system, sharia marketing mix, security, costs/assets, bank management, trust, customer income, religiosity, bank products, attitudes, norms, perceptions, intentions, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, avoid usury, deposit interest rates and number of offices. There is 1 study on each of these indicators.

Seventh, there are 5 indicators of customer interest in Mudharabah contract products at Sharia financial institutions, with a total of 5 studies, namely: (1) religiosity; (2) knowledge; (3) trust; (4) promotion; and (5) profit sharing ratio. There is 1 research object in these indicators.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Efforts to Develop Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

In this sub-chapter, the research subject regarding efforts to develop Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions is divided into 3 parts, namely:

First, there are 8 efforts to develop Mudharabah products at Sharia Financial Institutions in general, with a total of 10 studies, namely: (-) Marketing strategy for Mudharabah products, 2 studies; (-) Optimization of Mudharabah contracts, 2 studies; (-) Other development efforts, including: implementation of Mudharabah agreements in the form of equity-based crowdfunding, strategies for dealing with losses in Mudharabah contracts, learning about Mudharabah contracts in Islamic boarding schools, innovations in Mudharabah contracts, policies for dealing with the risk of losses in Mudharabah contracts and critical studies of Mudharabah practices in sharia banking. There is 1 study in these efforts.

Second, there are 11 efforts to develop Mudharabah financing products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 24 studies, namely: (-) Strategy for resolving problematic financing, 10 studies; (-) Mudharabah financing optimization strategy, 5 studies; (-) Other development efforts, including: risk reduction and performance escalation models for Mudharabah financing, Linked Waqf mudharabah for MSMEs, preventive efforts to maintain credibility and public trust, training on financing applications for MSMEs, benefits of Mudharabah Muqayyadah linkage financing products, optimization profit sharing of Mudharabah financing products in increasing profits and market share, analysis of the

feasibility of Mudharabah financing; marketing strategy for Mudharabah contract financing and counseling on the Mudharabah financing system for entrepreneurs. There is 1 study in each of these efforts.

Third, there are 6 efforts to develop Mudharabah deposit/savings products at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 6 studies, namely: (1) marketing strategy for Mudharabah deposit products; (2) customer recruitment strategy; (3) marketing strategy for Hajj savings; (4) Mudharabah-based farmer waqf banks in the agricultural sector; (5) marketing strategy for Mudharabah savings products; and (6) promotion mix strategy for Mudharabah Muthlaqah savings products.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Factors that Influence Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

In this sub-chapter, the research subject regarding the factors that influence Mudharabah contracts at Sharia Financial Institutions is divided into 10 parts, namely:

First, there are 14 factors that influence Mudharabah financing from the customer's perspective to the bank, with a total of 18 studies, namely: (-) Level of profit sharing, 5 studies; (-) Other factors, including: understanding, account officer, interest rates, character, capacity, conditions, guarantees/collateral, Islamic consumption, service quality, Islamic product attributes, Islamic business ethics, managing managers and accounting information. There is 1 study on each of these factors.

Second, there are 13 factors that influence Mudharabah financing from the bank's perspective to customers, with a total of 14 studies, namely: (-) Customer morality, 2 studies; (-) Other factors, including: high risk, customer reporting mechanism, influence of Non Performing Financing /NPF, customer transparency, difficult financing analysis, low customer understanding, ineffectiveness of Mudharabah financing, limited banks in intervening, HR capacity bank, lack of trust in customers, project attributes and mudharib. There is 1 study on each of these factors.

Third, there are 20 factors that influence Mudharabah financing from a bank perspective, with a total of 80 studies, namely: (-) Non Performing Financing /NPF, 16 studies; (-) Third Party Funds/DPK, 12 research; (-) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR and Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, 9 studies; (-) Return On Assets /ROA, 7 studies; (-) Profit sharing, 5 studies; (-) Mudharabah Deposits and Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO, 3 studies on each of these factors; (-) BI Rate, inflation, Mudharabah savings/deposits and interest rates, 2 studies on each of these factors; (-) Other factors, including: wadiah savings/current accounts, exchange rate, financial performance, capital, revenue sharing, liquidity, asset quality and problematic financing. There is 1 study on each of these factors.

Fourth, there are 4 factors that influence the level of return on Mudharabah financing from the customer's perspective, with a total of 4 studies, namely: (1) level of education; (2) number of family dependents; (3) business turnover; and (4) length of business.

Fifth, there are 23 factors that influence Mudharabah savings, with a total of 66 studies, namely: (-) Profit sharing level/ratio. There are 15 studies on this factor; (-) Inflation, 11 studies; (-) Deposit interest rates, 7 studies; (-) Gross Domestic Product/GDP and BI Rate, 4 studies on each of these factors; (-) Exchange rate and bank size, 3 studies on each of these factors; (-) National income, liquidity and number of branches, 2 studies on each of these factors; (-) Other factors, including: income, trust, sharia compliance, bank reputation,

information, economic growth, amount of money in circulation, LQ45, religiosity, promotional costs, Bank Indonesia/SWBI Wadiah Certificates, customer interests and perceptions, gender. There is 1 study on each of these factors.

Sixth, there are 13 factors that influence the profit sharing of Mudharabah savings, with a total of 38 studies, namely: (-) Financing to Deposits Ratio /FDR, 7 studies; (-) Non Performing Financing /NPF, 6 studies; (-) Return On Assets / ROA and Operational Costs to Operational Income / BOPO, 5 studies on each of these factors; (-) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR and financial ratios, 3 studies on each of these factors; (-) BI Rate and inflation, 2 studies on each of these factors; (-) Other factors, including: asset quality, Mudharabah financing, Return On Equity /ROE, total income and financial performance. There is 1 study on each of these factors.

Seventh, there are 24 factors that influence the level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits, with a total of 119 studies, namely: (-) Return On Assets / ROA and Financing to Deposits Ratio / FDR, 19 studies on each of these factors; (-) Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, 15 studies; (-) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR and Non Performing Financing /NPF, 10 studies on each of these factors; (-) Inflation, 9 studies; (-) Interest rates, 8 studies; (-) BI Rate, 5 studies; (-) Profit sharing ratio and financial performance, 4 studies on each of these factors; (-) Return On Equity /ROE and Gross Domestic Product/GDP, 2 studies on each of these factors; (-) Other factors, including: financing, operating income, bank performance, Third Party Funds/DPK, promotions, number of offices, Bank Indonesia Sharia Certificate/SBIS, exchange rate, operational profit, bank size, Mandatory Minimum Reserves/ GWM and Net Interest Margin / NIM. There is 1 study on each of these factors.

Eighth, there are 21 factors that influence Mudharabah deposits, with a total of 116 studies, namely: (-) Interest rates, 23 studies; (-) Inflation, 22 studies; (-) Level of profit sharing, 16 studies; (-) Profit sharing from deposits, 13 studies; (-) Financing to Deposits Ratio /FDR, 9 studies; (-) Gross Domestic Product/GDP and bank size, 5 studies on each of these factors; Number of offices, 4 studies; (-) BI Rate, 3 studies; (-) Foreign exchange rate, Return On Assets /ROA, liquidity and Non-Performing Financing /NPF, 2 studies each on these factors; (-) Other factors include: capital adequacy, problematic financing, Return On Equity / ROE, Operational Costs to Operational Income / BOPO, economic growth, exchange rate, profitability and cost efficiency. There is 1 study on each of these factors.

Ninth, there are 11 factors in determining the profit sharing ratio for Mudharabah financing, with a total of 12 studies, namely: customer business feasibility, Shariang revenue, good relationships with customers, total financing value, customer turnover, guarantees, regulations, bank policies, costs, competition and risk.

Tenth, there are 5 factors considered in determining the profit sharing ratio for Mudharabah savings, with a total of 5 studies, namely: (1) the rate applicable in other Sharia Banks; (2) good relations between the bank and customers/partners; (3) annual budget work plan; (4) placement of funds between banks; and (5) macroeconomic conditions.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Other Problems Related to Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

In this sub-chapter, the research subject regarding other matters relating to Mudharabah contracts at Sharia Financial Institutions is divided into 3 parts, namely:

First, there are 37 research topics regarding issues related to Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions in general, with a total of 48 studies, namely: (-) The effect of Mudharabah income on Return On Assets / ROA, 4 studies; (-) Guarantees in Mudharabah contracts, 3 studies; (-) Other issues relating to Mudharabah contracts in general, include: (1) determining the profit sharing ratio for Mudharabah contracts; (2) customer understanding of the Mudharabah concept; (3) obstacles to implementing the Mudharabah agreement; (4) the role of women in the Mudharabah agreement; (5) application of the principles of justice in the Mudharabah agreement; and (6) the effect of Mudharabah income on profitability; (7) the implications of mixing Mudharabah and Musyarakah contracts; (8) mutual fund investment using the Mudharabah system; (9) comparison of reward and profit sharing; (10) Mudharabah fund management; (11) dual status of intermediation institutions in carrying out Mudharabah contracts; (12) Mudharabah-based sharia engagement; (13) Mudharabah contract system for sharing profits and losses; (14) risks of Mudharabah contracts; (15) portrait of the implementation of the Mudharabah agreement during the time of the Prophet; (16) Mudharabah contract system in Islamic economics; (17) Patron Client semi-Mudarabah contract in agency theory in the fisheries sector; (18) Mudharabah agreement as a funding and financing instrument; (19) conversion of the Mudharabah contract to the Qardhu contract; (20) the concept of qiyas of the Mudharabah contract towards the Musaqah contract; (21) principles of justice and balance in drawing up a deed of limited partnership based on a Mudharabah agreement; (22) regulation of rights and obligations in the Mudharabah agreement; (23) application of profit-loss sharing in Mudharabah contracts; (24) sharia compliance of the Mudharabah agreement; (25) application of Mudharabah profit sharing; (26) the practice of Mawah contracting Mudharabah in Acehnese society; (27) implementation of Mudharabah investment on Umrah funds; (28) the influence of members' Mudharabah Third Party Funds (DPK) on Return On Equity /ROE; (29) perception of the implementation of the Mudharabah agreement; (30) comparison of the implementation of the Mudharabah agreement; (31) correlation between implementation of Mudharabah agreements and profitability; (32) the effect of savings and mudharabah financing on profitability; (33) the influence of profit sharing returns on the growth of Third Party Funds/TPF; (34) the effect of Mudharabah profit sharing income on net profit; and (35) the influence of Mudharabah transactions on company value. There are 2 studies on each topic number 1-6, and 1 study on each topic number 7-35.

Second, there are 41 research topics regarding problems related to Mudharabah financing at Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 92 studies, namely:

- Application of profit sharing and risk management of Mudharabah financing, 13 studies on each of these topics.
- Guarantees in Mudharabah financing, 9 research.
- Problems with Mudharabah financing and the influence of Mudharabah financing risk on bank profitability, 4 research on each of these topics.
- Mudharabah financing information system, Mudharabah financing procedures and moral hazard in Mudharabah financing, 3 research on each of these topics.
- Other problems related to Mudharabah financing include: (1) collateral in Mudharabah financing; (2) accounting for Mudharabah financing; (3) comparison of Kupedes credit and Mudharabah financing; (4) Application of the principles of justice in Mudharabah financing; (5) the effect of

financing profit sharing on profitability; (6) the effect of financing revenue sharing on MSMEs; (7) the effect of Mudharabah profit sharing on company profits; (8) effectiveness of the use of Mudharabah financing funds; (9) internal supervision of Mudharabah financing; (10) sharia ethical values in Mudharabah financing; (11) fines on Mudharabah financing; (12) comparison of Mudharabah financing and business credit; (13) dynamic relationship between Mudharabah financing risk and profitability; (14) comparison of the profit sharing system and the interest system; (15) profitability of Mudharabah financing; (16) the concept of debt in the Mudharabah financing agreement; (17) the principle of freedom of contract in Mudharabah financing; (18) analysis of internal control over Mudharabah financing; (19) risk of default on Mudharabah financing; (20) obstacles to Mudharabah financing; (21) sharia compliance division in Mudharabah financing; (22) return of Mudharabah financing; (23) allowance for impairment losses on Mudharabah financing; (24) calculation of profits from Mudharabah financing; (25) supervision of Mudharabah financing; (26) the principle of ikhtiyati in Mudharabah financing; (27) application of transparency principles in Mudharabah financing products; (28) the effect of Mudharabah financing income on profitability/ROA; (29) the effect of Mudharabah financing income on net profit; (30) the effect of financing revenue sharing on savings profit sharing; (31) the influence of Mudharabah Musyarakah Ratio (MMR) financing on Islamic Social Reporting (ISR); (32) the effect of Non Performing Financing Mudharabah on profitability; and (33) violation of the Mudharabah financing contract. There are 2 studies on each topic number 1-7, and 1 study on each topic number 8-33.

Third, there are 23 research topics regarding problems related to Mudharabah savings/deposits in Sharia Financial Institutions, with a total of 27 studies, namely:

- Accounting for raising funds using the Mudharabah principle, 3 studies.
- Calculation of profit sharing from Mudharabah deposits and the effect of profit sharing from Mudharabah deposits on profitability, 2 studies on each of these topics.
- problems related to Mudharabah savings/deposits include: (1) Mudharabah deposit investment risk; (2) conversion of savings into a Mudharabah savings contract; (3) Mudharabah investment with definite profit sharing; (4) comparison of returns on Mudharabah contracts and capital participation in raising funds for Islamic banks; (5) characteristics of customer fund deposit transactions; (6) risks and returns on Mudharabah deposit investments; (7) comparison of savings interest and profit sharing; (8) customer understanding of the Mudharabah agreement; (9) behavior of Mudharabah deposit customers towards profit sharing; (10) comparison of the quality of savings in Mudharabah Muthlaqah and Wadiah Yad Dhamanah contracts; (11) requests for Mudharabah savings by members; (12) application of prizes to Mudharabah savings products; (13) application of the principles of profit sharing and revenue sharing for Mudharabah savings and deposit products; (14) comparison of bonus calculations between interest and profit sharing; (15) comparison of the level of profit sharing between Mudharabah savings and own capital; (16) risk and return on Mudharabah deposits; (17) application of the principles of justice in depositing customer funds; (18) the effect of income sharing from Mudharabah deposits on Return On Assets / ROA; (19) the influence of the

profit sharing ratio on Mudharabah deposits on customer loyalty; and (20) the effect of Mudharabah deposits on net profit. There is 1 research on each of these topics.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Regarding Mudharabah Agreement on Sharia Bonds/Sukuk

In this sub-chapter, there are 10 research topics regarding Mudharabah contracts on sharia bonds/sukuk, with a total of 11 studies, namely: (1) Mudharabah sukuk as an ideal Islamic financial instrument; (2) the role of the trustee in the issuance of sharia bonds/mudharabah sukuk; (3) the influence of the issuer's internal factors on investors' profit sharing on sharia bonds/mudharabah sukuk; (4) the influence of profitability, efficiency and sharia compliance on Mudharabah sukuk yields; (5) the influence of inflation and SBI interest rates on returns on sharia bonds/mudharabah sukuk; (6) the influence of profitability, governance and company size on the Mudharabah sukuk rating; (7) market reaction to the announcement of the Mudharabah sukuk issuance; (8) Value at Risk of Mudharabah sukuk; (9) comparison of returns on Mudharabah sukuk and conventional bonds; and (10) income smoothing practices and potential displaced commercial risk in Sukuk Mudharabah. There are 2 studies on topic number 1, and 1 study on each topic number 2-10.

Conclusion and Suggestion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding Mudharabah contracts at Sharia Financial Institutions during the period 2001 to 2021 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 857 research articles.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the FEB Student Scientific Journal, Brawijaya University, Malang. The total number of publications is 27 research articles.
- The most productive researcher in publishing research results is Nana Diana, from Singaperbangsa University Karawang. The total number of publications is 6 research articles.
- In mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions are divided into 8 clusters. Cluster 1 consists of 101 topics, cluster 2 consists of 42 topics, cluster 3 consists of 20 topics, cluster 4 consists of 21 topics, cluster 5 consists of 15 topics, cluster 6 consists of 9 topics, cluster 7 consists of 4 topics and cluster 8 consists of 1 topic.
- Based on the Library Research, there are 8 main research themes surrounding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions, namely: (1) implementation of Mudharabah contracts, with a total of 29 topics and 104 studies; (2) the influence of the Mudharabah agreement, with 36 topics and 159 studies; (3) perspective of Islamic law, legislation and problems of Mudharabah contracts, with a total of 32 topics and 89 research; (4) indicators of customer loyalty, interest and satisfaction with Mudharabah contract products, with a total of 53 topics and 79 studies; (5) efforts to develop Mudharabah contracts, with 25 topics and 40 research; (6) factors influencing Mudharabah contracts, with a total of 148 topics and 472; (7) other problems related to Mudharabah Agreements, with a total of

102 topics and 167 research; and (8) Mudharabah contracts on Sharia Bonds/Sukuk, with a total of 10 topics and 11 studies.

Based on the conclusions above, the researcher suggests filling the gaps/shortcomings in 10 research publication topics regarding Mudharabah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions, namely: (1) Application of Mudharabah contracts in education funds/insurance, trade, livestock, fisheries, business capital and multi-contract sectors; (2) The influence of the Mudharabah agreement on profit sharing, economic growth/regional income, company value, liquidity, Sharia Maqashid Index and return on investment; (3) Legal problems regarding standard contracts, mitigating the risks of Mudharabah contracts, resulting conflicts and legal protection between banks and customers; (4) Indicators of customer loyalty towards Mudharabah financing/savings products and customer satisfaction with Mudharabah financing/savings products; (5) Efforts to develop Mudharabah contracts in terms of policies for overcoming risks, product innovation, overcoming losses and learning in Islamic boarding schools; (6) Factors that influence Mudharabah financing from the customer's perspective to the bank, and vice versa; (7) Factors that influence the rate of return on Mudharabah financing; (8) Factors in determining the profit sharing ratio for Mudharabah financing; (9) Factors considered in determining the profit sharing ratio for Mudharabah savings; and (10) Sukuk with a Mudharabah agreement.

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